

Primary Ovarian Pregnancy – A Rare Case Report

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ABSTRACT

A pregnancy confined to ovary accounts for upto 3% of all ectopic pregnancy and is the most common type of nontubal ectopic pregnancy. Ovarian ectopic can present as atypical presentation such as adnexal mass. A 26yr old female G4P2L1A1 presented in Gynaecology OPD with chronic dull aching generalized abdominal pain on and off since 5 months. Occasionally pain would radiate to the right shoulder. There was no history of amenorrhoea, syncopal attack and her menstrual cycles were normal. Patient was admitted and all necessary and emergency investigations were carried out. An ovarian ectopic pregnancy was found (fulfilling the Spiegelberg criteria) after exploratory laparotomy was performed.

KEY WORDS: adnexal mass, ectopic, ovarian, spiegelberg

INTRODUCTION:

A Pregnancy confined to the ovary accounts for upto 3% of all ectopic pregnancy and is the most common type of non tubal ectopic pregnancy. Unruptured ovarian ectopic is rare and is diagnosed if four clinical criteria are fulfilled outlined by Spiegelberg: 1) Ipsilateral tube is intact and distinct from the ovary; 2) Ectopic pregnancy occupies the ovary; 3) Ectopic pregnancy is connected by the utero-ovarian ligament to the uterus and 4) Ovarian tissue can be demonstrated histologically amid placental tissue.

11 per 1000 pregnancies are ectopic out of which 95% are tubal and 5% are Non tubal. Non tubal ectopic pregnancy is very rare but potentially life threatening. It is often misdiagnosed and can have rare presentations.

CASE REPORT:

A 26yr old female G4P2L1A1 presented in Gynaecology OPD with chronic dull aching generalized abdominal pain on and off since 5 months. Occasionally pain would radiate to the right shoulder. There was no history of amenorrhoea, no history of syncopal attack and her menstrual cycles were normal. Patient gave history of intake of unsupervised MTP

pills since past 5 months at the gestation period of 6 weeks. She gave history of suction and evacuation done at some private setup for uncontrolled bleeding, however no records or ultrasound report were available. After suction and evacuation patient stopped bleeding and resumed her regular menses.

On admission at our hospital, patient was clinically and haemodynamically stable. Per Abdomen Examination-Vague discomfort was felt on whole abdomen. Per Speculum Examination- Cervix grossly normal. Per Vaginal Examination- Uterus anteverted, normal size, mobile, an irregular mass of approximately size 4.3cm felt in the posterior fornix tender and fixed, no cervical motion & tenderness (Figure 3 & 4).

Investigations:

UPT – Positive, Hb-7.9g/dl, Beta HCG-271.60mIU/ml, CA-125-114.40U/ml. Ultrasonography – Heterogenous solid cystic mass lesion seen closely adherent to right ovary of size 5.5*2.8cm showing mild vascularity.

Hospital Course and Management:

After taking written and informed consent and blood arranged, patient was taken for exploratory laparotomy. There was intact pregnancy sac in the right ovarian fossa which was in the process of expulsion (Figure 1). Uterus and both tubes were normal and away from the mass. Gestational sac over the ovary, was removed gently (Figure 2). Corpus Luteum was on right ovary itself with bleeding surface. Haemostatic sutures were applied to the site (Figure 3). Few blood clots of 150 ml were removed from Pouch of Douglas. Post

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Figure1: Showing Intact sac in process of Expulsion.

Figure 2: Intact Bi lateral tubes and ovaries.

operatively single unit of blood was transfused. Patient. withstood procedure well. Histopathology report suggests Chorionic villi within the ovarian stroma suggestive of an ovarian pregnancy (Figure 4).

DISCUSSION:

Ovarian pregnancy is a rare variant of ectopic pregnancy and can have rare presentation of Adnexal mass. Early diagnosis of ovarian pregnancy is necessary in order to avoid more serious complications

Figure 3: Hemostatic suture applied over ovary.

and emergency invasive procedures.

However, preoperative diagnosis remains challenging. Its diagnosis is difficult and relies on criteria based on intraoperative findings and histopathology report. Its management remains surgical therapy despite the progress in medical treatment.

CONCLUSION:

High Index of suspicion of ectopic pregnancy should be there in women of reproductive age group presenting with amenorrhoea. Safe abortion practices

to be encouraged and confirmation of location of gestation should be done prior to prescribing medical abortion.

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Figure 4: Intact Gestational sac.

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